

Changes in PM_{2.5} concentrations and their sources in the US from 1990 to 2010

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Abstract

Significant reductions of emissions of SO₂, NO_x, volatile organic compounds (VOCs) and primary particulate matter (PM) took place in the US from 1990 to 2010. We evaluate here our understanding of the links between these emissions changes and corresponding changes in concentrations and health outcomes using a chemical transport model, the Particulate Matter Comprehensive Air Quality Model with Extensions (PMCAMx) for 1990, 2001 and 2010. The use of the Particle Source Apportionment Algorithm (PSAT) allows us to link the concentration reductions to the sources of the corresponding primary and secondary PM. The reductions in SO₂ emissions (64%, mainly from electric generating units) during these 20 years have dominated the reductions in PM_{2.5} leading to a 45% reduction in sulfate levels. The predicted sulfate reductions are in excellent agreement with the available measurements. Also, the reductions in elemental carbon (EC) emissions (mainly from transportation) have led to a 30% reduction of EC concentrations. The most important source of organic aerosol (OA) through the years according to PMCAMx is biomass burning, followed by biogenic secondary organic aerosol (SOA). OA from on-road transport has been reduced by more than a factor of three. On the other hand, changes in biomass burning OA and biogenic SOA have been modest. In 1990, about half of the US population was exposed to annual-average PM_{2.5} concentrations above 20 µg m⁻³, but by 2010 this fraction had dropped to practically zero. The predicted changes

37 in concentrations are evaluated against the observed changes for 1990, 2001, and
38 2010, in order to understand if the model represents reasonably well the
39 corresponding processes caused by the changes in emissions.

40

41 **1. Introduction**

42 During recent decades, regulations by the US Environmental Protection
43 Agency (EPA) have led to significant reductions of the emissions of SO₂, NO_x,
44 VOCs, and primary PM from electrical utilities, industry, transportation, and other
45 sources (EPA, 2011). Xing et al. (2013) estimated that, from 1990 to 2010, emissions
46 of SO₂ in the US were reduced by 67%, NO_x by 48%, non-methane VOCs by 49%,
47 and primary PM_{2.5} by 34%. An increase of ammonia emissions by 11% was estimated
48 for this twenty-year period. At the same time, there have been significant observed
49 reductions in the ambient PM_{2.5} levels in practically all areas of the US (Meng et al.,
50 2019). However, our ability to link these changes in estimated emissions with the
51 observed changes in PM_{2.5} faces challenges. The available PM_{2.5} composition and
52 mass concentration measurements are sparse in space and are quite limited before
53 2001. Three-dimensional chemical transport models (CTMs) are well suited to help
54 address this problem, since they simulate all the major processes that impact PM_{2.5}
55 concentrations and transport.

56 There have been several efforts to quantify historical changes in PM_{2.5} levels
57 and composition. These rely heavily on measurements (both ground and satellite for
58 the more recent changes) and on a number of statistical techniques including land-use
59 regression models to calculate the concentrations of PM_{2.5} over specific areas and
60 periods (Eeftens et al., 2012; Beckerman et al., 2013; Ma et al., 2016; Li et al.,
61 2017a). Milando et al. (2016) used positive matrix factorization (PMF) of PM
62 measurements to interpret the observed trends of PM_{2.5} from 2004 to 2011 in Detroit
63 and Chicago. They concluded that as secondary sulfate was declining, emissions from
64 biomass burning, vehicles and metals sources are becoming relatively more important.
65 More recent efforts also include applications of chemical transport models. For
66 example, Meng et al. (2019) estimated historical PM_{2.5} concentrations over North
67 America from 1981 to 2016 combining the predictions of GEOS-Chem, satellite
68 remote sensing, and ground-based measurements. That study focused on the
69 estimation of total PM_{2.5} levels to assess long-term changes in exposure and

70 associated health risks. The composition of PM_{2.5} and its sources were not analyzed in
71 that work. Jin et al. (2019) combined information from ground-based observations,
72 remote sensing and chemical transport models to estimate that the PM_{2.5}-related
73 mortality decreased by 67% in New York State from 2002 to 2012. Li et al. (2017a)
74 combined in-situ and satellite observations with the global CTM, GEOS-Chem, to
75 quantify global and regional trends in the chemical composition of PM_{2.5} over 1989–
76 2013. They concluded that the predicted average trends for North America were
77 consistent with the available measurements for PM_{2.5}, secondary inorganic aerosols,
78 organic aerosols and black carbon. Nopmongcol et al. (2017) used CAMx with the
79 Ozone Source Apportionment Technology (OSAT) and Particulate Source
80 Apportionment Technology (PSAT) algorithms for six different years within five
81 decades (1970-2020), to calculate the contributions from different emission sources to
82 PM_{2.5} and O₃ in the US. The same meteorology and the same natural emissions
83 (including wildfires) were used for all six simulated years. The authors concluded that
84 the contribution of electrical generation units (EGUs) and on-road sources to fine PM
85 has declined in most areas while the contributions of sources such as residential,
86 commercial, and fugitive dust emissions stand out as making large contributions to
87 PM_{2.5} that are not declining. The use of constant meteorology did not allow the direct
88 evaluation of these predictions.

89 In this study, we use period-specific meteorological data and source-resolved
90 emissions for every year simulated, to estimate the concentrations, composition, and
91 sources of PM_{2.5} over 20 years in the US. Three specific years are used as snapshots
92 of US air quality in time. Given that significant emissions changes have taken place
93 over the decades between the examined years, the predicted concentration changes
94 reflect mostly changes in these emissions plus some year to year meteorological
95 variability. The model predictions are compared with the available measurements.
96 The sources responsible for the PM_{2.5} reductions in various areas of the country are
97 identified and their contribution to the reductions is quantified. We also quantify
98 trends in population exposure and estimated health outcomes.

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103 **2. Model Description**

104 **2.1 PMCAMx**

105 PMCAMx (Karydis et al., 2010; Murphy and Pandis, 2010; Tsimpidi et al., 2010;
106 Posner et al., 2019) uses the framework of the CAMx model (Environ, 2006) to
107 describe horizontal and vertical advection and diffusion, wet and dry deposition, and
108 gas and aqueous-phase chemistry. A 10-size section (30 nm to 40 μm) aerosol
109 sectional approach is used to dynamically track the evolution of the aerosol mass
110 distribution. The aerosol species modeled include sulfate, nitrate, ammonium, sodium,
111 chloride, elemental carbon, mineral dust, and primary and secondary organics. The
112 Carbon Bond 05 (CB5) mechanism (Yarwood et al., 2005) is used in this application
113 of PMCAMx for gas-phase chemistry calculations. The version of CB5 used here
114 includes 190 reactions of 79 surrogate gas-phase species. For condensation and
115 evaporation of inorganic species, a bulk equilibrium approach was used, assuming
116 equilibrium between the bulk inorganic aerosol and gas phases. The partitioning of
117 each semi-volatile inorganic species between the gas and aerosol phases is determined
118 by the ISORROPIA aerosol thermodynamics model (Nenes et al., 1998). The mass
119 transferred between the two phases in each step is distributed to the size sections
120 using weighting factors based on the effective surface area of each size bin (Pandis et
121 al., 1993). Organic aerosols (primary and secondary) are simulated using the volatility
122 basis set approach (Donahue et al., 2006). For primary organic aerosols (POA), 8
123 volatility bins, ranging from 10^{-1} to $10^6 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ at 298 K saturation concentration are
124 used. Secondary organic aerosols (SOA) are split between aerosol formed from
125 anthropogenic sources (aSOA) and from biogenic ones (bSOA) and modeled with 4
126 volatility bins (1, 10, 10^2 , $10^3 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$) (Murphy and Pandis, 2009). NO_x -dependent
127 yields (Lane et al., 2008) are used. For better representation of the chemistry in NO_x
128 plumes, the Plume-in-Grid modeling approach of Karamchandani et al. (2011) has
129 been used for the major point sources following Zakoura and Pandis (2019).

130

131 **2.2 Particulate Source Apportionment Technology (PSAT)**

132 The PSAT algorithm (Wagstrom et al., 2008; Wagstrom and Pandis, 2011a, 2011b;
133 Skyllakou et al., 2014; 2017) is an efficient algorithm that tracks and computes the
134 contributions of different sources to pollutant concentrations. The advantages of
135 PSAT are that it runs in parallel with PMCAMx, so there is no need to modify the

136 CTM for different applications and that it is quite computationally efficient. PSAT
137 takes advantage of the fact that the molecules of each pollutant at each location
138 regardless of their source have the same probability of reacting, depositing, or getting
139 transported to avoid repeating the simulations of these processes. For secondary
140 species, it follows the apportionment of their precursor vapors. For example, the
141 apportionment of secondary organic aerosol is based on the apportionment of VOCs
142 or IVOCs, sulfate on SO₂, nitrate on NO_x, and ammonium on NH₃.

143 In this study, we use the version of PSAT developed by Skyllakou et al.
144 (2017) that is compatible with the Volatility Basis Set to calculate the contribution of
145 each emission source to the concentration of PM_{2.5} and its components.

146

147 **3. Model Application**

148 PMCAMx-PSAT was applied over the continental United States (CONUS) for the
149 years 1990, 2001, and 2010 using a grid of 132 by 82 cells with horizontal dimensions
150 of 36 km by 36 km (covering an area of 4752 × 2952 km) and 14 layers of varying
151 thickness up to an altitude of approximately 13 km. We selected this resolution as it
152 has been shown to be a viable option for keeping computational and storage demands
153 manageable while providing sufficient quality for long-term simulations and air
154 quality planning applications (Gan et al., 2016). This coarse resolution introduces
155 errors in areas where there are significant PM_{2.5} gradients in space including
156 California and urban areas in the rest of the western US.

157

158 **3.1 Meteorology**

159 Meteorological simulations were performed with the Weather Research Forecasting
160 model (WRF v3.6.1) over the CONUS area, with horizontal resolution of 12 x 12 km
161 and 36 vertical (sigma) levels up to a height of about 20 km. The simulations were
162 executed using 3-day reinitialization from observations. Initial and boundary
163 conditions were generated from the ERA-Interim global climate re-analysis database,
164 together with the terrestrial data sets for terrain height, land-use, soil categories, etc.
165 from the United States Geological Survey database. The WRF modeling system was
166 prepared and configured in a similar way as described by Gilliam and Pleim (2010).
167 For the model physical parameterization, the Pleim-Xiu Land Surface Model (Xiu and
168 Pleim, 2002) was selected. Other important WRF physics options used in this study

169 include the Rapid Radiative Transfer Model/Dudhia radiation schemes (Iacono et al.,
170 2008), the Asymmetric Convective Model version 2 for the planetary boundary layer
171 (Pleim, 2007a, 2007b), the Morrison double-moment cloud microphysics scheme
172 (Morrison et al., 2008), and version 2 of the Kain–Fritsch cumulus parameterization
173 (John et al., 2004). The selected WRF configuration is recommended for air quality
174 simulations (Hogrefe et al., 2015; Rogers et al., 2013).

175

176 **3.2 Emissions**

177 Emissions for the simulations were obtained from the internally consistent, historical
178 emission inventories of Xing et al. (2013) that include source-resolved gas and
179 primary particle emissions. Point source sectors include Electricity Generating Units
180 (EGU) included in the EPA’s Integrated Planning Model (IPM); industrial sources not
181 included in the IPM (non-EGU); and all other point sources in Canada and Mexico.
182 Area sources include on-road emissions in the US, Canada and Mexico; off-road
183 emissions for the entire domain; and all remaining non-biogenic sources. We used our
184 WRF meteorology to drive the Model of Emissions of Gases and Aerosols from
185 Nature (MEGAN3) (Jiang et al., 2018) using the default emission factors for all years
186 to generate biogenic emissions for the CONUS domain.

187 In this application of PSAT, we used 6 different emission categories based on
188 those described above plus initial and boundary conditions which are each tracked
189 separately by the model as different “sources”. As a result, the emission source
190 categories used are: ‘road’ which includes road emissions over the US; ‘non-road’
191 which includes the off-road emissions of the entire domain; ‘EGU’; ‘non-EGU’ as
192 described above; ‘other’ which includes the sum of the other point and area sources
193 plus the ‘on-road’ emissions from Canada and Mexico and finally biogenic emissions.
194 Figure 1 depicts the total annual emissions for each source and each year.

195 Biomass burning (included in the ‘other’ category) was the dominant source of
196 EC and remained relatively constant during the simulated period. The second most
197 important source of EC was road transport, with the corresponding emissions having
198 been reduced by a factor of 3.5 from 1990 to 2010. The overall reduction of EC
199 emissions was 40%.

200 Biomass burning and other sources, were the dominant source also for POA,
201 with almost constant contributions. Based on the emissions that Xing et al. (2013)

202 reported in the category ‘other’, we can estimate that biomass burning was
203 responsible for 46% of the total ‘other’ POA emissions. This contribution increased to
204 80% in 2001 and 83% in 2010. The PM emitted from biomass burning, according to
205 the inventory, is similar for these three years (Xing et al., 2013). The second most
206 important source of POA during 1990 was road transport contributing 5%. This
207 emission source was reduced by a factor of 3.5 from 1990 to 2010. Overall POA
208 emissions in the inventory were reduced by 27% from 1990 to 2010.

209 Emissions of VOCs by on-road sources were reduced by a factor of 3.5 during
210 these 20 years. On the other hand, the VOCs emitted by non-road transport decreased
211 by only 8%. The biogenic VOC emissions varied from year to year based on the
212 prevailing meteorology, but their changes were less than 20%. The total
213 (anthropogenic and biogenic) VOC emissions decreased by 31% from 1990 to 2010.

214 The emissions of the most important SO₂ source, EGUs, were reduced 33%
215 from 1990 to 2001 and 67% from 1990 to 2010. This resulted in a 64% reduction of
216 the total SO₂ emissions over these 20 years.

217 For NH₃, the most important source is agriculture (included in the ‘other’
218 category), and the corresponding emissions increased by 9% during these 20 years.

219 Road transportation is one of the major NO_x sources with the corresponding
220 emissions having been reduced by 21% from 1990 to 2001 and 58% from 1990 to
221 2010. The second most important source for NO_x in 1990, were the EGUs, which
222 emitted 25% less NO_x in 2001 and 66% less in 2010 compared to 1990. Total NO_x
223 emissions in the inventory were 47% lower in 2010 compared to 1990.

224

225 **4. Results**

226 **4.1 Annual-average concentrations and sources**

227 We examine first the source apportionment results of PMCAMx-PSAT for the major
228 components of PM_{2.5} for the three simulated years.

229 On-road transportation was a major source of EC especially in urban areas in
230 1990 (Figure 2). The EC concentrations originating from this source were reduced by
231 more than a factor of 3 from 1990 to 2010. The industrial sources (EGUs and non-
232 EGU) contributed less than 0.1 µg m⁻³ of EC in all areas during these years. The
233 ‘other’ source which includes all types of biomass burning was the most important

234 source during the simulated period. Long range transport (LRT), which represents the
235 transport from areas outside of the domain, contributed approximately $0.1 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$.

236 The predicted average total OA levels defined as the sum of POA and SOA
237 are shown in Figure 3. The OA originating from road transport was about $0.7 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$
238 during 1990 over the Eastern US, but it was reduced to less than $0.5 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ during
239 2010. ‘Non-road’ transport and ‘non-EGU’ emission sources had smaller
240 contributions to OA, with less than $0.2 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ in most areas during all years. Biogenic
241 SOA was almost $1 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ over the south-east US both during 1990 and 2001, but
242 during 2010 it had higher concentrations in some areas. Especially in the South due to
243 local meteorology predicted SOA was much higher compared to 1990. In 2010, the
244 biogenic VOC concentrations were on average 15% higher compared to 1990 due
245 mainly to the meteorological conditions during these two specific years. This small
246 increase is consistent with the biogenic VOC emissions estimated by Sindelarova et
247 al. (2014). Also, high OA concentrations were predicted to originate from biomass
248 burning during 1990. The average contribution of long-range transport OA was
249 approximately $0.6 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$.

250 Sulfate was the dominant component of $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ in the Eastern US in 1990 and
251 the EGUs were its dominant source contributing more than $5 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ over wide areas
252 of the East (Figure 4). The corresponding sulfate concentrations from EGUs were
253 reduced to $3 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ in 2001 and to $1.5 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ in 2010 due to the dramatic reduction of
254 these SO_2 emissions over these 20 years. Sulfate concentrations originating from non-
255 EGU and other emission sources were $1 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ or less during all years. Long-range
256 transport contributed approximately $0.9 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ to the sulfate levels during the
257 simulated period.

258

259 **4.2 Evaluation of the model predictions**

260 The model was evaluated both on an annual and daily basis against ground-level
261 measurements from the IMPROVE and CSN networks (STN U.S. EPA, 2002;
262 IMPROVE, 1995). The metrics used in the main analysis, include the normalized
263 mean bias (NMB), the normalized mean error (NME), the mean bias (MB), the mean
264 absolute gross error (MAGE), the fractional bias (FBIAS), and the fractional error
265 (FERROR) (Fountoukis et al., 2011):

266

$$\begin{aligned}
267 \quad NMB &= \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (P_i - O_i)}{\sum_{i=1}^n O_i} & NME &= \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n |P_i - O_i|}{\sum_{i=1}^n O_i} \\
268 \quad MB &= \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (P_i - O_i) & MAGE &= \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n |P_i - O_i| \\
269 \quad FBIAS &= \frac{2}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{(P_i - O_i)}{(P_i + O_i)} & FERROR &= \frac{2}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{|P_i - O_i|}{(P_i + O_i)}
\end{aligned}$$

270 where P_i represents the model-predicted value for site i , O_i is the corresponding
271 observed value and n is the total number of sites. During 1990, there were only 27
272 measurement sites for $PM_{2.5}$ composition, all parts of the IMPROVE network, but this
273 number increased dramatically in 2001 to more than one hundred and 2010 to
274 approximately three hundred stations. There was almost an order of magnitude more
275 measurements and stations for just $PM_{2.5}$ mass concentration. The results for annual
276 evaluation are summarized in Table 1 and for the evaluation based on daily average
277 concentrations in Table 2.

278 PMCAMx reproduced the annual average $PM_{2.5}$ concentrations with an
279 absolute fractional bias less than 16% and fractional error less than 25% (Table 1).
280 The highest bias was found for 1990, when measurements from only 33 sites were
281 available. During 2001 and 2010 when more than 1000 stations were operational the
282 $PM_{2.5}$ fractional bias was only 5%. The model tends to underpredict $PM_{2.5}$ in the sites
283 in the West and especially in California and tends to overpredict in the rest of the
284 country (Table S1). The OA annual average concentrations were also reproduced with
285 little bias (less than 5%) and fractional error less than 30%. The model had a slight
286 tendency towards overprediction of sulfate with a fractional bias of 17-28%
287 depending on the year but the fractional error was still modest at 23-37%. The EC
288 annual levels were reproduced with little bias (FBIAS equal to 6-8%) during 1990 and
289 2010, but there was tendency towards overprediction during 2001 (FBIAS=28%)
290 while the fractional error was modest (28-39%). The nitrate levels especially in the
291 high nitrate areas were underpredicted (FBIAS ranged from -28% to -41%) and the
292 error was relatively high compared to all other components (54-61%). Finally, the
293 model did a relatively good job reproducing the ammonium levels (FBIAS 4-17% and
294 FERROR 26-29%). The low grid resolution of these simulations introduced
295 significant errors in California where significant spatial gradients are encountered.
296 The evaluation results without the Californian sites are summarized in Table S2. For

297 example, the nitrate bias is reduced (as an absolute value) to -19% to -34% when the
298 measurements in California are excluded from the evaluation.

299 According to Morris et al. (2005), the level of the performance of the model
300 for daily resolution is considered excellent if it meets the following criteria: FBIAS \leq
301 ± 0.15 and FERROR ≤ 0.35 ; good if FBIAS $\leq \pm 0.30$ and FERROR ≤ 0.50 ; is average
302 if FBIAS $\leq \pm 0.60$ and FERROR ≤ 0.75 ; and is problematic if: FBIAS $> \pm 0.60$,
303 FERROR > 0.75 . Based on these criteria, the ability of the model to reproduce the
304 daily average concentrations during all simulated years is good for PM_{2.5}, average for
305 EC, OA, sulfate, ammonium, and problematic for nitrate. The daily PM_{2.5}
306 concentrations, for which there are many more stations and measurements in 2001
307 and 2010, are reproduced with fractional bias of 3 to 13% and fractional error less
308 than 50% (Table 2). For 1990, there is little bias, while there is a small tendency
309 towards overprediction in the later years.

310 The version of PMCAMx used in these simulations has difficulties
311 reproducing the nitrate levels. There several reasons for these problems including the
312 spatial resolution used here, the assumption of bulk equilibrium, etc., that will be
313 analyzed further in future work. PMCAMx has a small tendency towards
314 underprediction of the OA and the EC. There is also a tendency towards
315 overprediction of the sulfate and as a result, the ammonium too.

316 We also followed the approach suggested by Emery et al. (2017) for the
317 characterization of the model performance. This approach relies on the NMB, NME
318 and correlation coefficient (r) as metrics. The results of the corresponding analysis are
319 summarized in Tables S4, S5 and S6 and suggest that the model is acceptable for all
320 components and periods with two exceptions: sulfate during 2010 and ammonium
321 during 2001.

322 One of the important results of this evaluation is the relatively consistent
323 performance of PMCAMx during the different years. The use of a consistent emission
324 inventory, consistent meteorology and measurements have probably contributed to
325 this outcome.

326

327 **4.3 Regional contributions of sources to PM_{2.5} components**

328 The US was divided in seven regions (Fig. 5) to facilitate the spatial analysis of the
329 source contributions and their changes during the simulated period. The Northeast

330 (NE) region includes major cities such as New York, Boston, Philadelphia, Baltimore
331 and Pittsburgh, while the Mideast (ME) includes the Ohio-river valley area with a
332 number of electrical generation units. The Midwest (MW) has significant agricultural
333 activities, while much of the West (WE) is relatively sparsely populated. California
334 (CA) was kept separate from the other western regions. The southern US was split
335 into a southeast region (SE) with significant biogenic emissions and the southwest
336 (SW) with much less vegetation.

337 Figure 6a shows the predicted average concentrations of EC for each year in
338 each region. The highest concentrations for 1990 were predicted in Northeast,
339 followed by the Mideast and the California. Biomass burning, included in the 'other'
340 source, was the dominant source of EC in all regions, with relatively constant
341 concentration through the years, except from CA, where the contribution from this
342 source in 1990 was much higher due to the annual variation in fires. There was
343 significant reduction of the EC levels in all regions except for the West, where the EC
344 originates mainly from biomass burning and long-range transport. The highest
345 reductions were predicted for the eastern US. Figure 6b shows the population
346 exposure (Walker et al., 1999), which is calculated in this work as the product of the
347 average annual concentration of each computational cell times the population living in
348 the cell. The US population distribution was calculated for each year based on the US
349 Census Bureau (2019) data and is different for 1990, 2001 and 2010. The population
350 distribution of 2001 is assumed to be the same with that of 2000. The population
351 exposure is significant in areas with high population density, for example in CA. The
352 US population increased from 1990 to 2010 by almost 24%. This increase would have
353 led to a corresponding increase in total population exposure if the emissions had not
354 changed during this period.

355 The source contributions to the annual-average concentrations of OA are
356 depicted in Figure 7a. The predicted concentrations of OA in 1990 in the eastern US
357 (NE, SE and ME regions) were almost $3 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ and in the other regions, less than 2.5
358 $\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$. OA originating from biomass burning dominated the concentrations of OA
359 during all years and regions. Biogenic SOA was the second most significant OA
360 component in the Southeast. OA originating from on-road transport contributed,
361 according to the model, almost $0.5 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ during 1990 and almost $0.2 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ during
362 2010 in the eastern US. Significant reductions of OA are predicted for the Northeast,

363 Mideast, and California while moderate reductions for the Midwest, West, and
364 Southwest. The OA in the Southeast has more complex behavior due to the predicted
365 increase of biogenic SOA in 2010 that leads to a small increase of the total OA
366 compared to 2001. The population exposure for OA (Figure 7b) is almost the same for
367 Northeast and Mideast during 1990 and it decreased during 2001 and 2010. For the
368 Midwest, West, and Southwest the population exposure to OA remained almost
369 constant though the years. For all regions, the highest population exposure was due to
370 biomass burning and the “other” sources. In addition, 20% of the population exposure
371 was due to road transport during 1990 at the highest populated areas (NE, ME, and
372 CA), but this percentage was reduced to almost 10% during 2010.

373 The highest concentrations of sulfate for 1990 are predicted in the Eastern US
374 (NE, ME and SE) in regions downwind of the EGUs which are the dominant SO₂
375 source in these areas (Fig. 8a). The drastic reductions of the EGU emissions are
376 predicted to have led to major reductions in the sulfate levels in these three regions.
377 More modest, but significant reductions of sulfate are also predicted for the Midwest
378 and the Southwest. The reductions in the West and in California from the EGU source
379 are small given that the sulfate there even in the 1990s was relatively low and was
380 dominated on average by long-range transport. Regarding the population exposure for
381 NE and ME, the percentage of population exposure due to EGUs during 1990 was
382 58% for the NE and 64% for the ME, but during 2010 these percentages were reduced
383 to 44% and 53% respectively.

384 The mortality rates caused by total PM_{2.5} were also calculated for the three
385 simulated periods, following the relationships of Tessum et al. (2019) and using the
386 death rates of US population by Murphy et al. (2013). We estimated 861 deaths per
387 100,000 persons for 1990, 777 for 2001, and 658 for 2010.

388

389 **4.4 Linking average changes in emissions, concentrations, and exposure**

390 The 72% reduction of emissions of EC from road transport, from 1990 to 2010
391 according to PMCAMx led to a 72% reduction of EC concentrations and a 70%
392 reduction in human exposure to EC from this source (Table 3). The changes in
393 concentrations are practically the same as those of the emissions because EC is inert
394 and the atmospheric processes that affect it (transport and removal) are close to linear.
395 The small difference between the change in emissions and that of exposure is due to

396 small differences in the spatial distributions of the EC concentrations from road
397 transport and the population density. The differences are small because most road
398 transport emissions are in densely populated areas. The similarity in the fractional
399 change of emissions and concentrations applies as expected to all EC source types
400 (Table 3). However, for all these other sources the reduction in exposure is less than
401 the reduction in emissions (or concentrations). For example, the 44% reduction of EC
402 emissions from non-road transport, was accompanied by a 43% reduction in
403 concentrations, but a 35% reduction of human exposure. This is due to the location of
404 the reductions of these non-road transport emissions. A significant fraction of these
405 reductions took place away from densely populated regions (e.g., in agricultural
406 regions) therefore they resulted in a smaller reduction of human exposure. The
407 situation is a little different for total EC. The 40% reduction in emissions is predicted
408 to have led to a 31% reduction in concentration. The difference here is due to the
409 contribution of long-range transport (sources outside of the US) which are assumed to
410 have remained approximately constant during this period. The predicted reduction in
411 exposure is 33% and is due to the local sources. The changes in EC exposure in each
412 region are depicted in Figure 6b.

413 The changes in fresh POA are a little more interesting because it is treated as
414 semi-volatile and reactive in PMCAMx. For all US sources, the reduction in
415 concentrations is a little higher than that of the emissions (Table 3). For example, a
416 25% reduction of POA emissions of non-road POA, is predicted to have resulted in a
417 30% reduction of the POA concentrations. This difference is due mostly to the non-
418 linear nature of the partitioning of these emissions between the gas and the particulate
419 phase. As the emissions are reduced, the corresponding OA concentrations are
420 reduced and more of the organic material is transferred to the gas phase to maintain
421 equilibrium. This additional evaporation leads to an additional reduction of the POA
422 concentrations. This is the case for all sources, so the 27% reduction in POA
423 emissions corresponds according to PMCAMx to a 33% average reduction in POA
424 concentrations. The reduction in exposure is, in absolute terms, a little less than that
425 of the concentrations for the same reasons as for EC. This difference is small (-74%
426 versus -71%) for road transport, but more significant for sources located outside urban
427 centers (e.g. for EGU it is -13% for concentrations and -6% for exposure).

428 The reductions predicted by PMCAMx for SOA (aSOA+bSOA)
429 concentrations are far more complex than those of fresh POA, since the formation of
430 secondary organic species involves non-linear processes such as partitioning,
431 dependence on oxidant levels, NO_x-dependence of the yields, and the complexity of
432 the chemical aging. Overall, PMCAMx predicts that the reductions in exposure are
433 less than the reductions in average concentrations over the US which are also less than
434 the reductions in the emissions of the anthropogenic volatile and intermediate
435 volatility organic compounds. One explanation of this behavior is that the
436 simultaneous decreases in NO_x levels have led to increased SOA formation yields. A
437 second factor is the time required for the formation of SOA especially when multiple
438 generations of reactions are required. The result of this time delay is SOA is often
439 produced away from its sources located in high urban density areas. The reasons for
440 this complex behavior will be analyzed in detail in future work.

441 The predicted reductions in sulfate concentrations are less than the reductions
442 in emissions due mainly to the non-linearity of the aqueous-phase conversion of SO₂
443 to sulfate (Seinfeld and Pandis 2016) (Table 3). Such non-linearity has been predicted
444 also in past CTM applications (Karydis et al., 2007; Tsimpidi et al., 2007). Taking
445 into account the transport of some of the sulfate from areas outside of the US, the
446 model predicts that the 64% reduction in SO₂ emissions has resulted in a 45%
447 reduction of the sulfate concentration on average. The reduction in exposure is a little
448 less, 40% on average, because both the major sources of SO₂ are located and the
449 higher reductions of sulfate take place, according to PMCAMx, away from the major
450 urban centers.

451

452 **4.5 Distribution of population exposure to PM_{2.5} from different sources**

453 We have calculated the percentage of people exposed to different PM_{2.5}
454 concentrations from the major sources ('other', 'EGUs', 'road transport') for the three
455 different periods. Almost half of the US population was exposed to PM_{2.5}
456 concentrations above 20 µg m⁻³ in 1990. A decade later this percentage was less than
457 20% and close to zero during 2010 (Fig. 9a). During 1990, almost 90% of the US
458 population was exposed to PM_{2.5} concentrations above 10 µg m⁻³, the suggested
459 annual mean by the World Health Organization (WHO, 2006). This percentage was
460 reduced to 83% in 2001 and 70% in 2010 (Fig. 9a and Fig. S2h).

461 The predicted distribution of the population exposed to PM_{2.5} from the source
462 'other' in 1990 covered a wide range extending from approximately 1 to 16 µg m⁻³.
463 The exposure from these sources was reduced significantly in the following years
464 mainly due to the reductions in the emissions of paved/unpaved road dust, prescribed
465 burning, and industrial emissions (Xing et al., 2013). The average emissions from
466 wildfires did not change appreciably, but this distribution was sharper in 2010, with
467 maximum percentages of people exposed appearing for PM_{2.5} concentrations ranging
468 from 5 to 8 µg m⁻³. The random spatial variation of biomass burning sources can
469 affect areas with different population density.

470 The exposure of the population to primary and secondary PM_{2.5} from EGUs
471 has been dramatically decreased (Fig. 9c). In 1990 according to PMCAMx 56% of the
472 US population was exposed to more than 3 µg m⁻³ from this source. This percentage
473 was reduced to 39% in 2001 and to 2% in 2010. For the threshold of 5 µg m⁻³ the
474 reduction was from 18% in 1990, to 1% in 2001 to practically zero in 2010.

475 Similarly, significant decreases are predicted for road transport PM_{2.5}. While
476 in 1990, 79% of the population was exposed to levels exceeding 1 µg m⁻³, this
477 percentage was 58% in 2001 and 18% in 2010 (Fig. 9d). The corresponding changes
478 for the 2 µg m⁻³ were from 27% (1990) to 8% (2001) to zero (2010).

479

480 **4.6 Predicted spatial changes of concentrations**

481 We calculated the predicted changes in annual-average concentrations between 1990
482 and 2010 for the main PM_{2.5} components. Figure S3 shows the reductions in EC
483 concentrations from 1990 to 2010. The reductions of the EC emissions resulted in
484 total reductions of the average concentrations of around 30% in the twenty-year
485 period. Reductions above 20% are predicted not only in the large urban areas but also
486 in large regions in both the eastern and the western US.

487 Average organic aerosol levels were reduced according to PMCAMx by close
488 to 1.5 µg m⁻³ from 1990 to 2010 in a wide area extending from the Great Lakes to
489 Tennessee, but also in parts of the Eastern seaboard (Fig. S4). These reductions
490 correspond to 35-45% of the OA in both the Northeast and California.

491 From 1990 to 2010, sulfate was reduced by 50-60% in the part of the country
492 to the east of the Mississippi. The corresponding reductions in the middle of the
493 country and in the western states from 1990 to 2010 were in the 20-30% range for the

494 relatively low sulfate levels in these regions (Fig. S5). These simulations suggest that
495 the Eastern US has benefited more both in an absolute and in a relative sense from
496 these reductions in SO₂ emissions.

497 We also compared the predicted and observed concentration changes, using
498 the Pearson's correlation coefficient and the average percentage differences,
499 summarized in Table 4. Also, as for as the exposure changes are concerned, because
500 of the way that exposure is defined (concentration times population) and the
501 population is measured, the evaluation metrics of our exposure predictions are exactly
502 the same as the evaluation metrics of our concentration predictions. For the first two
503 cases (1990 to 2001 and 1990 to 2010) there were only a few measurements available
504 for 1990. The model reproduces quite well the predicted changes against the observed
505 for PM_{2.5} and its components (Fig. S6).

506 For EC, the correlation was high between 1990 and 2001, with $r = 0.80$; and
507 between 1990 and 2010, with $r = 0.91$. However, the analysis for the changes up to
508 2010 is complicated by the change in the EC measurement protocol in several CSN
509 sites in the period from 2007 to 2010. The change from the Thermal Optical
510 Transmittance (TOT) to the Thermal Optical reflectance (TOR) resulted in small
511 increases in the reported EC that were of similar magnitude as the predicted changes
512 due to the emissions reductions. To partially address this issue, we do not include in
513 the analysis the results from 14 CSN sites which reported increases in the EC from
514 2001 to 2010. Excluding these sites an $r = 0.39$ is calculated (Table 4). The data
515 points from these sites can be seen in the lower triangle of Fig. S6. The reduced r for
516 the 2001-10 is probably due, at least partially, to this uncertainty of the measured
517 changes.

518 The predicted average change of OA in the measurement sites from 1990 to
519 2001 was -13%, in good agreement with the observed -16% in the same locations.
520 The predicted changes were reasonably well correlated ($r = 0.68$) with the measured
521 ones during this decade. However, the model performance during the next decade
522 (2001-10) deteriorates as it underpredicts on average the changes (predicted -9%
523 versus observed -18%) and the changes are not correlated to each other in space.
524 Additional analysis suggested that, while the model does a reasonable job reproducing
525 the changes in the western half of the country and the northeastern quarter, it
526 overpredicts the OA concentration in 2010 and thus underpredicts the reductions in

527 the southeastern US. Our analysis also suggests that this mainly due to an
528 overprediction of the biogenic SOA in this part of the country. This is consistent with
529 the anomalous predicted increase of biogenic SOA from 2001 to 2010 in the SE US
530 (Figure 7 and Figure S1). This interesting discrepancy regarding the predicted and
531 observed changes of biogenic SOA will be analyzed in detail in a subsequent paper.

532 For sulfate, the model reproduced well the observed changes for the three
533 comparison periods, with Pearson's correlation coefficient $r = 0.88$ (from 1990 to
534 2001); 0.97 , from 1990 to 2010; and 0.92 , from 2001 to 2010 (Table 4). Despite the
535 nonlinearity in the behavior of sulfate, the average predicted and observed percentage
536 changes were consistent for the three comparison periods.

537 Finally, for $PM_{2.5}$ the model reproduces well the observed changes for the
538 three comparison periods with $r = 0.81$ (from 1990 to 2001); 0.82 (from 1990 to 2010)
539 and 0.61 (from 2001 to 2010). The average percentage changes for the observations
540 and the predictions were close for all the cases (Table 4).

541

542 **5. Conclusions**

543 The CTM, PMCAMx, was used to simulate the changes in source contributions to
544 $PM_{2.5}$ and its components over two decades accounting for changes in emissions and
545 meteorology with internally consistent methods. Biomass burning and 'other' sources,
546 primarily including construction processes; mining; agriculture; waste disposal, and
547 other miscellaneous sources, contributed approximately half of the total (primary and
548 secondary) $PM_{2.5}$ during the examined 20-year period. The corresponding average
549 $PM_{2.5}$ concentration levels due to this group of sources have been reduced by 33%
550 from 1990 to 2010. EGUs were the second most important source of $PM_{2.5}$; the
551 corresponding ambient $PM_{2.5}$ levels have been reduced by 55% and their contribution
552 to the total from 16% to 11%. On-road transport was the third most important source
553 of $PM_{2.5}$. The total average $PM_{2.5}$ from this source was reduced by 59%, while their
554 contribution to the average $PM_{2.5}$ levels has been reduced from 8% to 5%.

555 OA was a significant fraction of $PM_{2.5}$. Biomass burning included in the
556 'other' sources was the most important source of OA with fractional contributions
557 varying from 38% to 52% depending on the region. Biogenic SOA was the second
558 dominant component of OA with contributions ranging from 6% to 22% in the South
559 US.

560 The relationship between the changes in concentrations and changes in
561 exposure is determined by the spatial distributions of these two changes. The more
562 similar these distributions are, the closer the corresponding changes. The reduction in
563 exposure was less than the reduction in emissions (or concentrations) for sources that
564 are located away from densely populated regions (non-road transport and non-EGUs)
565 due to the spatial non-uniformity of the corresponding PM_{2.5} reductions. For example,
566 sulfate human exposure by non-EGU source was reduced by 46% from 1990 to 2010,
567 while the corresponding reduction in emissions was 62%.

568 From 1990 to 2010, the reduction of human exposure to EC was 33%, to fresh
569 POA 35%, to sulfate 40%, and to SOA (both anthropogenic and biogenic) 8%. The
570 reduction of EC was mostly due to the 72% reduction of on-road EC emissions, while
571 the reduction in sulfate to the 64% reduction of SO₂ emissions from EGUs.

572 Considering that the US population increased by almost 24% from 1990 to
573 2010, the fact that the total population exposure to PM was reduced in most areas
574 indicates that the emission reductions were sufficient to overcome this effect. The
575 decreases in personal exposure have been higher than these of the total population
576 exposure.

577 During the 20 year-long examined period, the fraction of the US population
578 exposed to average PM_{2.5} concentrations above 20 µg m⁻³ decreased from
579 approximately 50% to close to zero. In 1990, 12% of the US population was exposed
580 to PM_{2.5} concentrations lower than the suggested annual mean by the WHO (10 µg
581 m⁻³). This fraction increased to 30% in 2010.

582 PMCAMx reproduced the annual average concentrations of PM_{2.5} with
583 fractional error less than 30% for the three simulation periods. The corresponding
584 fractional biases were 16% for 1990 and 5% for both 2001 and 2010. The model also
585 reproduces well the average reduction of PM_{2.5} in the measurement sites; the
586 measured reduction was 28% while the model predicts a reduction of 30%. A model
587 weakness that requires additional investigation is its tendency to predict an increase in
588 the biogenic SOA from 2001 to 2010 that appears inconsistent with the observations.

589

590 **6. Code and data availability**

591 The code and simulation results are available upon request
592 (spyros@chemeng.upatras.gr).

593

594 **7. Supplement**

595

596 **8. Author contributions**

597 K.S performed the PMCAMx and PSAT simulations, analyzed the results and wrote
598 the manuscript. P.G.R. prepared the anthropogenic emissions and other inputs for the
599 simulations. B.D. performed MEGAN simulations and analyzed the results; E.K.
600 performed and evaluated the WRF simulations; I.K. set-up the WRF simulations and
601 assisted in the preparation of the meteorological inputs. C.H. analyzed the simulation
602 output. S.N.P. and P.J.A. designed and coordinated the study and helped in the writing
603 of the paper. All authors reviewed and commented on the manuscript.

604

605 **9. Competing interests**

606 The authors declare that they have no conflict of interest.

607

608 **10. Acknowledgments**

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613

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785

786 **Table 1:** Evaluation metrics for annual average concentrations of PM_{2.5} and for its
 787 major components for each examined year.

	MB ($\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$)	MAGE ($\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$)	NMB	NME	FBIAS	FERROR	Stations
EC							
1990	-0.01	0.07	-0.01	0.23	0.08	0.28	33
2001	0.13	0.18	0.39	0.56	0.28	0.39	122
2010	-0.05	0.16	-0.11	0.35	0.06	0.39	304
OA							
1990	-0.05	0.49	-0.02	0.21	0.05	0.23	33
2001	-0.29	0.66	-0.12	0.28	-0.01	0.28	121
2010	0.05	0.60	0.02	0.27	0.05	0.26	306
Sulfate							
1990	0.13	0.22	0.09	0.16	0.19	0.23	33
2001	0.17	0.38	0.13	0.30	0.28	0.37	118
2010	0.08	0.30	0.05	0.18	0.17	0.27	327
Nitrate							
1990	-0.13	0.28	-0.30	0.65	-0.38	0.61	33
2001	-0.26	0.40	-0.24	0.37	-0.28	0.54	114
2010	-0.35	0.41	-0.35	0.41	-0.41	0.55	321
Ammonium							
1990	-0.06	0.16	-0.09	0.25	0.04	0.26	33
2001	-0.01	0.21	0.00	0.23	0.08	0.28	113
2010	0.06	0.18	0.08	0.23	0.17	0.29	326
PM_{2.5}							
1990	1.04	1.64	0.16	0.26	0.16	0.25	33
2001	0.94	2.92	0.08	0.24	0.05	0.24	1040
2010	0.71	2.16	0.07	0.22	0.05	0.24	1067

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793 **Table 2:** Evaluation metrics for daily average concentrations of PM_{2.5} and for its
 794 major components for each examined year.

	MB ($\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$)	MAGE ($\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$)	NMB	NME	FBIAS	FERROR	Points	Comment
EC								
1990	-0.03	0.16	-0.11	0.53	0.14	0.57	2940	Average ^a
2001	0.10	0.27	0.28	0.71	0.38	0.62	18763	Average
2010	-0.04	0.23	-0.10	0.54	0.23	0.60	29423	Average
OA								
1990	-0.03	0.16	-0.11	0.53	0.14	0.58	2940	Average
2001	-0.45	1.37	-0.17	0.53	0.05	0.55	18706	Average
2010	-0.01	1.20	-0.01	0.56	0.15	0.54	29412	Average
Sulfate								
1990	0.14	0.62	0.11	0.47	0.31	0.53	3228	Average
2001	-0.02	0.95	-0.01	0.45	0.25	0.54	18077	Average
2010	0.18	0.76	0.12	0.52	0.34	0.58	33051	Average
Nitrate								
1990	-0.11	0.40	-0.26	0.99	-0.78	1.29	2998	Problematic
2001	-0.30	0.81	-0.31	0.83	-0.62	1.11	18019	Problematic
2010	-0.33	0.66	-0.34	0.68	-0.74	1.13	30867	Problematic
Ammonium								
1990	-0.05	0.30	-0.09	0.48	0.14	0.52	2996	Average
2001	-0.03	0.49	-0.03	0.54	0.24	0.58	17828	Average
2010	0.05	0.39	0.08	0.54	0.33	0.60	30162	Average
PM_{2.5}								
1990	0.74	2.73	0.13	0.50	0.16	0.46	2706	Good
2001	1.27	5.43	0.11	0.46	0.13	0.44	161909	Good
2010	-0.02	4.33	0.00	0.45	0.03	0.47	212899	Good

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796 ^a Following Morris et al. (2005) criteria: Good: FBIAS $\leq \pm 0.30$, FERROR ≤ 0.50 ;
 797 Average: FBIAS $\leq \pm 0.60$, FERROR ≤ 0.75 ; Problematic: FBIAS $> \pm 0.60$, FERROR
 798 > 0.75

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801 **Table 3:** Percentage changes in emissions from each source, and corresponding
 802 changes in average concentrations and exposure from 1990 to 2010.

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	Road	Non-road	EGU	Non-EGU	Biogenic	Other	Total
EC							
1990 to 2010							
Emissions (EC)	-72	-44	-13	-7	-	-17	-40
Concentrations	-72	-43	-13	-8	-	-18	-31
Exposure	-70	-35	-3	4	-	-12	-33
Fresh POA							
1990 to 2010							
Emissions (fresh POA)	-72	-25	-13	-14	-	-25	-27
Concentrations	-74	-30	-13	-20	-	-31	-33
Exposure	-71	-25	-6	-11	-	-32	-35
SOA							
1990 to 2010							
Emissions (IVOCs+VOCs)	-71	-8	-8	-31	15	-34	-31
Concentrations	-71	-17	-11	-21	23	-27	-21
Exposure	-66	-6	1	-8	37	-18	-8
Sulfate							
1990 to 2010							
Emissions (SO₂)	-93	-51	-67	-62	-	-52	-64
Concentrations	-91	-44	-63	-54	-	-38	-45
Exposure	-88	-30	-60	-46	-	-27	-40

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813 **Table 4:** Average observed and predicted PM percentage changes, and Pearson's
 814 correlation coefficient calculated for each comparison case.

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	Observed changes (%)	Predicted changes (%)	Pearson's r	Number of Sites
EC				
1990 to 2001	-19	-12	0.80	21
2001 to 2010	-19	-17	0.39	75 ^a
1990 to 2010	-45	-24	0.91^b	21
OA				
1990 to 2001	-16	-13	0.68	21
2001 to 2010	-18	-9	-0.32	89
1990 to 2010	-33	-23	-0.16	21
Sulfate				
1990 to 2001	-9	-9	0.88	21
2001 to 2010	-35	-22	0.92	75
1990 to 2010	-40	-29	0.97	21
PM_{2.5}				
1990 to 2001	-10	-14	0.81	21
2001 to 2010	-21	-20	0.61	636
1990 to 2010	-28	-30	0.82	21

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817 ^a 14 CSN sites reporting increases of EC, probably due to the change in the
 818 measurement protocol in the 2007-09 period, have been excluded from this analysis.

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820 ^b The correlations in bold are statistically significant for a significance level of 5%.

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825 **Figure 1:** Annual emissions by each source for the whole domain for: a) elemental

826 carbon, b) fresh POA, c) non-methane VOCs, d) SO₂, e) NH₃, and f) NO_x.

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835 **Figure 2:** Predicted annual average ground level PM_{2.5} elemental carbon
 836 concentrations per source for 1990, 2001, and 2010.

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839 **Figure 3:** Predicted annual average ground level PM_{2.5} organic (primary plus
 840 secondary) aerosol concentrations per source for 1990, 2001, and 2010. The EGU
 841 contributions are low and are not shown.

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844 **Figure 4:** Predicted annual average ground level $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ sulfate concentrations per

845 source for 1990, 2001, and 2010. The on-road, non-road, and biogenic contributions

846 are low and are not shown.

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Figure 5: Definition of the 7 regions used in the analysis.

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870 **Figure 6:** Sources of PM_{2.5} EC for the different regions during 1990, 2001, and 2010

871 for: a) average concentrations ($\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$) and b) population exposure (persons $\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$).

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876 **Figure 7:** Sources of $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ OA for the different regions during 1990, 2001, and 2010

877 for: a) average concentrations ($\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$) and b) population exposure (persons $\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$).

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884 **Figure 8:** Sources of PM_{2.5} sulfate for the different regions during 1990, 2001, and

885 2010 for: a) average concentrations ($\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$) and b) population exposure (persons μg

886 m^{-3}).

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894 **Figure 9:** Distributions of population exposed to annual average PM_{2.5} during 1990

895 (grey), 2001 (red), 2010 (blue); and for the dominant sources of PM_{2.5}: a) road

896 transport, b) EGU, c) other, and h) total PM_{2.5}.

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